

PRINCIPLES OF THE CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM AND PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH TO STUDENTS

Yusupov Farrukh Islom ugli

State Conservatory of Uzbekistan

Chief specialist of the credit module department

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Abstract: In this article, the understanding of the module-credit system created in the system of higher education, as well as the advantages of this system for students, as well as the positive and negative aspects of the module-credit system, and the pedagogical views of students about this system are widely covered.

Key words: Educational system, credit module, independent education, pedagogical activity, individual activity, independent thinking.

Introduction.

Today, the system of teaching and evaluating students in a modern way has been put into practice in the higher education system. The credit-module system is considered as a student evaluation system in a higher education institution, and this system was introduced to make it easier for students and facilitate their education.

On October 8, 2019, our honorable president signed the decree "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". In this important program, it is determined to gradually transfer the educational process to the credit-module system in higher education institutions. Also, by 2030, 85 percent of all higher education institutions in the republic will be transferred to the credit-module system¹.

The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an assessment model based on a set of module technologies and a credit measure. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process. In the credit module principle, two main issues are given importance: ensuring independent work of students; assessment of student knowledge based on rating. Among the main conditions of this form of the system, the following are mentioned:

- organization of educational processes on the basis of modules;
- determining the value of one aan, course;
- evaluation of students' knowledge based on rating score;
- to create an opportunity for students to create their study plans individually;
- increasing the share of independent education in the educational process.

All of the above are called not only to conduct teaching on the basis of innovative educational technologies, but also to learn independently from the student, and to have a new attitude to education. In short, this system is aimed at the professional development and maturity of the student.

The introduction of this credit-module system in higher education will increase the quality of teaching, ensure efficiency, eliminate corruption, reveal the real knowledge of the

¹ Decree of the President of October 8, 2019 PA-5847.

student and allow the student to study and work on himself independently. creates the ground. The introduction of the module is an important factor in the cooperation between the teacher and the student. In modular education, the pedagogue organizes, manages, advises and checks the student's learning process. The student moves independently towards the directed object. The largest part also allows students to study independently².

Independent education becomes more important in the educational process and leads to an increase in independence, individuality, creative initiative and activity of future specialists. In the credit-module system, students of higher education always have the opportunity to receive help and advice from teachers and fellow students. This strengthens mutual cooperation and helps to develop teamwork skills. The transition to the credit-module education system increases the obligation and demand for the teachers of the higher educational institution. From a pedagogical point of view, the leadership role of the teacher is preserved. Also, the credit system of education increases student exchange. Because the credits received in one higher education are taken into account for the other, and students can transfer from one university to another without losing credits. This system provides an opportunity for students of our country to continue their studies in advanced foreign universities and to remove complex obstacles. However, it should be noted that the direct application of any international experience blindly, without taking into account our own values, without a deep analysis of each of its elements, is a scientific basis. it is necessary not to forget that certain negative situations will occur in the future, as long as it is not carried out with confidence³.

The main issues of importance in the credit-module system are as follows:

- ensuring independent work of students;
- evaluation of students' knowledge based on rating;
- production and improvement of modular teaching technology;
- to further improve the methodical support of science to ensure independent activity of students.

² Orinov V. Credit-module system in higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan: basic concepts and rules. Study guide.

³ Usmanov B. SH., Khabibullayev R.A. Organization of the educational process in higher educational institutions in the credit-module system. Study guide. - Tashkent, TKTI, 2020. - page 120.

It is known that the credit-module system is based on certain principles. Below we will briefly touch on the implications of each principle:

organization of student-centered learning;
achieve transparency in education;

improving flexibility in education (improving
alexibility);

improving student mobility.

Organization of student-centered education Educational systems can generally be divided into two categories: teacher-centered and student-centered. In a teacher-centered education system, education, curricula, and teaching processes are approached strictly from the perspective of higher education, its controlling organization, and the teacher's wishes. The needs and opinions of the representatives of the labor market and students are not taken into account when determining what, how much, and how students should learn. Management and organization of the educational process is carried out in a very centralized way. In this case, the teacher is considered as the only source of knowledge. Students are mainly formed as passive listeners because the educational processes do not encourage them to be active (lessons are organized mainly in the form of lectures). In such an educational system, students do not have the ability to think independently, express their opinions, engage in discussion, critically approach problems, and make decisions for themselves. Student-centered education is the opposite of teacher-centered education.

The educational system is aimed at forming the potential of students to think independently, share their knowledge with others, and make decisions for themselves. Students have their own curriculum by having some degree of self-selection of subjects. Through this feature in education, students are not able to learn more about the subjects and directions they are interested in, take a critical approach, and make their own decisions. Student-centered education is the opposite of teacher-centered education.

Students have their own curriculum by having some degree of self-selection of subjects. Through this feature in education, students have the opportunity to study the subjects and directions they are interested in more deeply, to successfully complete their student period, to fully realize their potential and to make their own decisions. they did. It is a qualitative change process aimed at improving students' independent learning and critical thinking skills in the learning environment and is an outcome-based approach. Student-centered learning is based on the following elements:

- active learning of the student;
- emphasis on critical and analytical learning and understanding;
- increasing the student's responsibility and accountability;
- increase the student's independent learning;
- using the reflective approach of students and professors-teachers in the educational process.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it is possible to say that the credit-module system created convenience for students even though it was improved as a novelty. It is no exaggeration to say that such reforms implemented in the higher education system in the current globalization process are one of the most important reforms being created for students

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